

INDIVIDUALIZED INSTRUCTION METHODOLOGY IN ENGLISH TEACHING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8022951>

Annotation: In the modern socio-economic conditions of our society, the main task of education is to educate and educate a competitive person and citizen who is able to think creatively and find non-standard solutions to various problems. The modern lesson has always been the subject of professional disputes. Carefully observing the students, the teacher sees that some of them have unstable attention, it is difficult for them to concentrate on the educational material, others strive for mechanical memorization of the rules, and others are slow in work.

Key words: memorization, special subjects, individual, classrooms, backgrounds, differentiated, flexibility.

Ecological theorists such as Bronfenbrenner point to the importance of the settings and circumstances in which students live for understanding children's behavior and establishing productive programs and policies to promote the development of children and youth. Teachers make many decisions that can be informed by an understanding of the context in which children live. These decisions include curricular and instructional decisions about materials and methods used in the classroom. Teacher's guidance of children's classroom learning can be fostered by understanding how the knowledge, practices, and language socialization patterns within children's families and communities contribute to children's ability to function in the classroom, how to communicate and work with children's families, as well as how to promote children's participation and positive social relations in the classroom.

The developmental psychology during the latter part of the 20th century was influenced both by neo-Vygotskian thinking and by the cognitive revolution. Cognitive developmental psychology contributed research findings and ideas about how children learn that have enormous implications for teacher education. For one, in contrast to presenting teachers with global stage models of cognition, studies of problem-solving suggest that teachers need to understand how children approach and solve specific types of problems within content areas and how the development of domain-specific reasoning is linked to everyday reasoning. Another line of work underscores the importance of attending to metacognition given the oft-endorsed goals of fostering intentional and competent learners.

Yet other scholars have drawn attention to the role of discourse and interpretive communities in learning. Finally, others have advanced knowledge about children's theories of mind and epistemology.

Each perspective, whether the contemporary constructivist, social constructivist or ecological perspective, or the out of vogue entity, moderationist or behaviorist view, suggests certain practices and implies particular qualities that are valued in teachers and students. In turn, as argued in the next section, those views are all operating today and can be linked to classroom practices.

Recently, Olson and Bruner argued that educational practices are based on teachers' views or folk psychologies, their beliefs about children, learning, and knowledge. Drawing upon contemporary research in child development, Olson and Bruner identified four general models of children and pedagogy typically held by teachers. In their framework, less sophisticated folk psychology perspectives concentrate on children's behavior, view learning as imitation, and conceptualize teaching as presenting information, whereas more sophisticated views conceive of children as competent and intentional meaning makers and of education as a process of forming, identifying, questioning, weighing, and producing ideas based on evidence subject to scrutiny. They also note that an understanding of Children's socioemotional development is necessary for effective teaching but do not identify and explicate those views and associated pedagogy. Most importantly, their framework invites us to conceptualize teachers as developing people, an idea that has often been overlooked.

Olson and Bruner identify four folk psychology concepts of the child as a doer, knower, thinker, or expert with associated ideas about what students acquire in school (skill/ability, knowledge, beliefs, and expertise, respectively) and the abilities that make learning possible (ability to do, learn, think, and contribute to cultural store, respectively). Olson and Bruner also associate views of folk psychology with folk pedagogical views of the roles of the teacher and student. In the present article, perspectives are identified from the psychological literature, rather than from folk psychology. Five general views of mind drawn from the psychological literature: nativist, fixed intelligence (entity), behaviorist, constructivist, and social constructivist are presented with hypothesized relations between those views of the mind of the child, valued qualities of teachers, endorsed classroom practices, and valued qualities of the child in school. The particular classroom practices endorsed and used by those with such views represent an extension of Olson and Bruner's framework. The identification of teachers' views of children's social emotional development along with related beliefs and practices represents another extension of Olson and Bruner's framework.

Children have a reputation for being natural language learners, for very good reason. Almost without exception, they have learned their native language with apparent ease, and by the time they are 6 years old they have brought it to a level of fluency that is the envy of non-native speakers. Parents who bring their children into a second-language setting and immerse them in a new situation for example, an elementary school taught in the foreign language often experience a kind of miracle. After around 6 months, their child begins to function successfully in the new setting and at a linguistic level to which the parents cannot hope to aspire, even when they have been studying the language seriously for a similar period of time. These examples of children's natural language learning ability might seem to suggest that the best thing to do to help a child learn a language is simply to place the child in the target language setting and then stay out of the way to let the miracle happen. Unfortunately, this is not an approach that will make it possible to bring languages to every child. There is, however, both linguistic and psychological theory to help explain children's seemingly effortless second-language acquisition and to provide insights that can make the classroom a better place for such language acquisition to take place. Understanding this theory, showing consideration of learner differences, and understanding the principles of child development and the characteristics of children at different stages of development will help prepare the

teacher to create curriculum and activities that bring languages and children together effectively.

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